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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

A LEGEND FOR A ROMAN PREFECT: THE LAKES OF
PONTIUS PILATE¹

PART 2

9. An unexpected Christian

In our previous articles, we have outlined the figure and traits of Pontius Pilate, a historical character who actually lived in the first half of the first

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century and held a high-rank post as prefect of the Roman province of Judaea, according to the ancient classical sources. The man is described as a wicked, ruthless person, who used to pay little or no heed at all to local customs, showing a substantial neglect of his subjects' needs and expectations, particularly when it came to religious affairs. Corruption and abuse were commonplace under his administration, and the opinions held on him by writers such as Philo of Alexandria and Flavius Josephus were definitely in the negative. Aspects of cowardice and sadistic cruelty can also be highlighted in the available descriptive excerpts.

The same Pontius Pilate also plays a key role in the tragic events related to the Passion and death of Jesus Christ, as described in the Gospels of John, Matthew, Mark and Luke. In the listed Christian sources, Pilate conducts himself essentially in a cowardly way, scared of the roaring mob and fearing that his ineptitude might be reported to his ultimate boss in Rome, Emperor Tiberius.

However, despite the adverse picture painted by both the Gospels and non-Christian authors, in the first centuries of Christianity Pilate was considered as a sort of positive figure: a man who had made repeated though faint attempts at saving Jesus' life («I find no fault in him», he had told the Jews more than once), a Roman leader who appeared to be on the verge of an early conversion to the new blossoming religion, right under the shadow of the Cross.

Unbelievable as it may seem, as early as the end of the second century, a Christian author, Quintus Septimius Florens Tertullianus, in his *Apologeticum*, spent words to cast a very favorable light on the Roman prefect. Let's read them from the eleventh-century manuscript Latin 1656A, preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (folium 156v):

«All these things with reference to Christ, Pilate, who himself also in his own conscience was now a Christian, reported to the then emperor Tiberius».

[In the original Latin text: «Ea omnia super Christo Pilatus, et ipse iam pro sua conscientia Christianus, Caesari tunc Tiberio nuntiavit»].

Fig. 58 - Pontius Pilate as a Christian from Quintus Septimius Florens Tertullianus' *Apologeticum* (manuscript Latin 1656A, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, folium 141r with the opening of Tertullianus' work and the excerpt from folium 156v)

In Tertullianus' opinion, Pontius Pilatus was so impressed by the deeds and miracles reportedly accomplished by Jesus Christ that not only he became a sort of undisclosed Christian devotee, but he also succeeded in convincing Emperor Tiberius himself of the divine nature of the crucified man (*Apologeticum*, folium 144v):

«Thus Tiberius, in whose time the Christian name first made its appearance in the world, laid before the senate tidings from Syria Palestine which had revealed to him the truth of the divinity there manifested, and supported the motion by his own vote to begin with. The senate rejected it because it had not itself given its approval. But Caesar held to his own opinion and threatened danger to the accusers of the Christians».

[In the original Latin text: «Tiberius ergo, cuius tempore nomen Christianum in saeculum introiuit, adnuntiata sibi ex Syria Palaestina, quae illic veritatem ipsius divinitatis revelaverant, detulit ad senatum cum praerogativa suffragii sui. Senatus, quia non ipse probaverat, respuit, Caesar in sententia mansit, comminatus periculum accusatoribus Christianorum»].

From this first, very early literary passage, we see that Pontius Pilate, the vicious prefect who certainly did not spend so great an effort to save Jesus from his doom of torture and death, in the first centuries of Christianity

began to be turned into a well-intentioned administrator who, all in all, wasn't that bad as it might have appeared at a first glance; and this positive view also applied to his imperial counterpart in Rome, Tiberius.

Fig. 59 - Tiberius favours Christians, from Tertullianus' *Apologeticum* (manuscript Latin 1656A, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, folium 144v)

Was that of Tertullianus an isolated opinion? No, as he was not the only early-Christian author to hold this belief. Let's read the following words, which were written in Greek by Eusebius of Caesarea, a fourth-century bishop and historian, in his *Historia Ecclesiae* (Book II, Chapter II), the way this excerpt appears in the eleventh-century manuscript Grec 1431 preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (folium 29r), in which we highlighted the Greek words for 'Pilate' and 'Tiberius':

«Pontius Pilate reported to Emperor Tiberius about the resurrection of our saviour Jesus from the dead, as the news were already spreading across Palestine. He also gave an account of other wonders which he had learned of him, and how, after his death, having risen from the dead, he was now believed by many to be a God. They say that Tiberius referred the matter to the Senate, but that they rejected it, ostensibly because they had not first examined into the matter, and the voice of the people had anticipated its decision on the issue. In fact there was an ancient law that no one should be made a God by the Romans except by a vote and decree of the Senate. In reality the recognition of a divine nature certainly needed no confirmation and recommendation by any man. So, as we stated above, the Senate rejected that proposition; yet Tiberius still retained the opinion which he had held at first, and contrived no hostile measures against the new Christian religion».

Fig. 60 - The excerpt on Pilate as it appears in Eusebius of Caesarea's *Historia Ecclesiae* (manuscript Grec 1431, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, folium 1r with the opening of Eusebius' work, folium 26v bearing the initial portion of Book II, Chapter II, and folium 29r with the passage which mentions Pilate and Tiberius, with the two names highlighted)

And we may also quote from Paulus Orosius, an early-Christian theologian and historian who lived between the fourth century and the fifth, who was specifically mentioned by Antoine de la Sale in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*. Once again, in Orosius' *Historiarum adversus paganos* (Book 7, IV) we find a further description, possibly drawn from the same Tertullianus, of a bewildered Pontius Pilate, who appears to be so amazed at the tales on Jesus Christ which were reported to him that he persuaded his Emperor in Rome, too, of the verity of the new religion. We take this passage from a most ancient manuscript, dating back to the ninth century (no. 545 (499), Bibliothèque Municipale de Valenciennes, folia 105v and 106r):

«When the Lord Christ had suffered and risen from the dead and had sent forth His disciples to preach, Pilate, the governor of the province of Palestine, made a report to the Emperor Tiberius and to the Senate concerning the passion and resurrection of Christ, and also the subsequent miracles that had been publicly performed by Him or were being done by His disciples in His name. Pilate also stated that a rapidly increasing multitude believed Him to be a god. When Tiberius, amid great approval, proposed to the Senate that Christ should be considered a god, the Senate became indignant because the matter had not been referred to it earlier in

accordance with the usual custom, so that it might be the first to pass upon the recognition of a new cult. The Senate therefore refused to deify Christ and issued an edict that the Christians should be banished from the City. There was also the special reason that Sejanus, the prefect of Tiberius, was inflexibly opposed to the recognition of this religion. Nevertheless in an edict Tiberius threatened denouncers of Christians with death».

Fig. 61 - Pontius Pilate and Tiberius from Paulus Orosius' *Historiarum aduersus paganos* (no. 545 (499), Bibliothèque Municipale de Valenciennes, folia 2r, 105v and 106r)

[In the original Latin text: «at postquam passus est Dominus Christus atque a mortuis resurrexit et discipulos suos ad praedicandum dimisit, Pilatus, praeses Palaestinae prouinciae, ad Tiberium imperatorem atque ad senatum retulit de passione et resurrectione Christi consequentibusque uirtutibus, quae uel per ipsum palam factae fuerant uel per discipulos ipsius in nomine eius fiebant, et de eo, quod certatim crescente plurimorum fide deus crederetur. Tiberius cum suffragio magni fauoris retulit ad senatum, ut Christus deus haberetur. Senatus indignatione motus, cur non sibi prius

secundum morem delatum esset, ut de suscipiendo cultu prius ipse decerneret, consecrationem Christi recusavit edicto que constituit, exterminandos esse urbe Christianos; praecipue cum et Seianus praefectus Tiberii suscipiendae religioni obstinatissime contradiceret. Tiberius tamen edicto accusatoribus Christianorum mortem comminatus est»].

So, was Pilatus really to be held guilty for the death of Jesus Christ, the Saviour, the Son of God?

According to early-Christian writers, the answer was no. Pilate, Tiberius and the Romans weren't ultimately to be considered as the perpetrators of such a crime. Actually a much easier target was to be found near at hand, as shown in the following sentence:

«It was not so much Pilate that condemned Him (he knew that 'for envy the Jews had delivered Him'), as the Jewish nation instead, which has been condemned by God, and rent in pieces, and dispersed over the whole earth, in a degree far beyond what happened to Pentheus».

Fig. 62 - Pilate, Pentheus and the Jews as mentioned by Origen of Alexandria in his *Kata Kelsou* (manuscript Grec 616, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 20r with the first page of the treatise and folium 76v with the relevant excerpt and the Greek words for 'Pentheus' and 'Pilate' highlighted)

This passage is drawn from an ancient Christian treatise, *Kata Kelsou* (*Against Celsum*, Book II), as it appears in manuscript Grec 616 preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (folium 76v). These words were written by Origen of Alexandria, a Christian theologian and scholar who lived between the end of the second and the beginning of the third century. He quotes from the Gospel of Mark («for he knew that the chief priests had delivered him for envy», 15:10), and compares the tragic destiny of the Jews to that of Pentheus, the King of Thebes who was dismembered out of a divine punishment (we will soon meet this King again in a later article).

Thus, the basic idea was that the guilt for the killing of a God did not lay with Pontius Pilate: instead, the blame was to be put on the Jewish nation.

The evil seeds of a ghastly doctrine, Anti-Semitism, had just been planted. And that doctrine would ravage across future centuries.

Sadly enough, this racist course of thought has deeply marked the Christian mentality up to the present days, together with this odd idea of an alleged innocence of Pilate. For instance, more than a thousand years later we find a trace of this very same idea re-stated in a version of St. Jerome's *Commentary on Matthew* edited by the great Dutch scholar Erasmus of Rotterdam and published in 1537 (the words below were not written by fifth-century theologian St. Jerome, as they are not present in earlier manuscripts bearing the text of his *Commentarius in Matthaeum*, therefore being a sixteenth-century interpolation by Erasmus, as scholars maintain):

«Pilate gave multiple opportunities for freeing the Savior: first by offering a thief for a just man; then by adding: "What then shall I do about Jesus who is called Christ? [...] what evil has he done?" In saying this, Pilate absolved Jesus. [...] Thus, in the washing of his hands, the actions of the Gentiles are cleansed, and in some manner he estranges us from the impiety of the Jews».

[In the original Latin text: «Multas liberandi salvatoris Pilatus occasiones dedit. Primum latrone iusto conferens. Deinde inferens: Quid igitur faciam de Iesu qui dicitur Christus [...] Quid eum mali fecit. Hoc dicendo Pilatus absolvit Iesum. [...] Ut in lavacro manuum eius, gentilium opera purgarentur, et ab impietate Iudaeorum [...] nos alienos faceret»].

Fig. 63 - Erasmus of Rotterdam's edition of St. Jerome's *Commentary on Matthew*, published in Basel in 1537, with sentences on Pilate which are not present in earlier manuscripts bearing the work by St. Jerome

But let's stick to the first centuries of the Christian era. In the next article, we will continue our exploration of a surprisingly good, unexpectedly Christian Pontius Pilate.

A Pilate who is going to be promoted to a much higher position: that of a saint.

10. The man who saw the truth

As we saw in our previous article, in the first centuries of Christianity Pontius Pilate, the fifth prefect of Judaea who had played a major role in the Passion of Jesus, was considered as a sort of pagan herald of the Salvation, despite his manifest responsibilities in the events that led to the death of the Saviour: he began to be seen as a man who had not intended to condemn the Son of God, and as a representative of the Roman Empire

who had just yielded to the pressure of the Jews, a governor who had even submitted passionate reports to his Emperor in which he maintained that the Christians were the followers of a true God.

Fig. 64 - Pontius Pilate and the Cross

In this view, held by many early-Christian authors, Pilate was seen as a person who had felt, in his own soul, the call of the Spirit, as portrayed in the early fifth century by Augustine of Hippo in his *Homiliae de tempore*, “*In festo Epiphaniae domini, Sermo III*:

«Pilate as well had received a whiff of the truth, when in the title which he put on the cross he wrote: 'King of the Jews', that the mistaken Jews tried to amend. And Pilate replied to them: 'What I have written I have written', for the Psalm had said 'The writing on the title shall not be corrupted'».

[In the original Latin text: «Hinc et Pilatus nonnulla utique aura veritatis afflatus est, quando in eius passione titulum scripsit: Rex Iudaeorum: quem Iudaei conati sunt mendosi emendare. Quibus ille respondit: Quod scripsi, scripsi: quia praedictum erat in Psalmo: Tituli inscriptionem ne corrumpas»].

Actually Pilate was in good company, because Augustine, in his *De civitate Dei*, had already enrolled the classical Sibyls, too, in this very same prophesying role (see our previous paper *World of the Sibyl: the Italian Apennines and the Sibillini Mountain Range*).

Fig. 65 - Pontius Pilate as a witness to the truth from St. Augustine of Hippo's *Homiliae de tempore*, Sermo III of *In festo Epiphaniae domini* (from *Tomus decimus operum divi Aurelii Augustini Hipponensis episcopi*, printed in Paris in 1555, pag. 136).

However Pontius Pilate's transformation is not yet over.

Because the key to his changing figure and tradition, a ghost-like, ever-transforming semblance journeying across the centuries, is to be retrieved in a much more shadowy territory than that of known, reputable classical authors we already quoted from, such as Philo of Alexandria, Flavius Josephus, Origen of Alexandria, Tertullianus, Eusebius of Caesarea, Paulus Orosius and Augustine of Hippo.

We must address the obscure, indistinct world of the apocryphal writings.

Out of the canonical list of books formally accepted by the Church since the Council of Rome held in the year 382, the apocryphal writings tell more

on Jesus and his life and Passion than the agreed-upon Gospels of Matthew, Mark, Luke and John. Yet their origin, authorship and editing history are often unknown or poorly known, and the adherence of their narrative to actual truth, or at least to the original underlying traditions, is questionable and hard to trace.

Fig. 66 - The heading 'Apocrypha' which appears in an edition of the Bible printed in London in 1606 by Robert Barker (pag. 358)

Despite all that, the fascinating, controversial character of Pontius Pilate is one of the main figures addressed by some of the apocryphal writings. From the *Epistola Pilati* to the *Gesta Pilati*, from the *Anaphora Pilati* to the *Paradosis Pilati*, up to the *Legenda Aurea*, the prefect of Rome who, willingly or unwillingly, sentenced Jesus to death, makes his appearance in many ancient writings.

For better or for worse.

Let's start from the better: the many apocryphal representations of the Roman prefect which portray Pilate as a deeply troubled man, a person who had assisted to the grievous deeds of the killing of a righteous, and had the chance to behold the subsequent portentous events, so impressive that he himself had begun to believe that that crucified man was really a God, and had written about all he had seen in his official reports addressed to the Emperor in Rome.

A man who had started his own personal journey into faith, and sanctity.

11. The hunt for the official report

When Jesus Christ underwent his harrowing Passion, Pontius Pilate was holding a high-rank post in Judaea as prefect of the province occupied by the Romans. According to Flavius Josephus, he had been appointed by Emperor Tiberius Caesar (*The Jewish War*, Book II, 169), and to Tiberius, who was still in full power when the Passion occurred, he was bound to report all the events that had happened in that remote and riotous fragment of the Roman Empire.

Did Pilate ever write an official report on the Passion?

And if he did, where is that report?

The question has absorbed the attention of early Christianity for centuries. An official report written by Pontius Pilate and addressed to his Emperor would be the ultimate evidence, generated by an independent, reliable source, of the actual truth of the Passion, and possibly of the Resurrection, too. A sort of smoking gun: a special one, as it would be the proof of the Incarnation of a God on earth.

Fig. 67 - An artist's impression of the much-sought original report written by Pontius Pilate to the Emperor in Rome with reference to the Passion

Has such a fateful piece of papyrus or parchment ever existed?

Justin Martyr, a Christian apologist who lived in the second century, was convinced that it was just the case: in Chapters XXXV and XLVIII of his “First Apology”, addressed to Emperor Antoninus Pius, he notes that «you can read all about that [the Passion of Jesus] in the official reports which were written by Pontius Pilate», and «the reports written by Pilate provide you with the proof of those events».

We already saw that Tertullianus, in his second-century *Apologeticus* (Chapter XXI, 24), wrote that «all these things with reference to Christ, Pilate [...] reported to the then emperor Tiberius» (in the original Latin text: «ea omnia super Christo Pilatus [...] Caesari tunc Tiberio nuntiavit»). And in the fourth century Eusebius of Caesarea, in his *Historia Ecclesiae* (Book II, Chapter II, 1-3), reiterated this same belief: «Pontius Pilate informed Tiberius of the reports [...] concerning the resurrection of our Saviour Jesus from the dead» (in the Latin translation from the original Greek text: «De resurrectionem a mortuis domini et salvatoris nostri Iesu Christi [...] Pilatus Tiberio principi refert»).

If Pontius Pilate's report has ever been written in actual reality, the original item has long gone lost amid the mists of the millennia.

Yet, something has survived. A report written by the Roman prefect who played a major part in Jesus' death. Actually, more than one report: there are many of them.

Let's start from the oldest one: an ancient tradition has handed down to us a letter that Pilate would allegedly have written to Emperor Claudius, one of the successors of Tiberius. Some scholars date it to the end of the second century, and surely it is the most ancient representative of the Christian apocryphal tradition concerning Pontius Pilate.

This text is often found as a section of the *Gospel of Nicodemus*, an apocryphal work including different narratives, as it appears for instance in manuscript Vat Lat 4363 preserved at the Vatican Apostolic Library. Of course, the letter, which allegedly contains the original, much sought-after official report on the Passion that Pontius Pilate, in his capacity as prefect

This is the opening of the letter. In a few lines, Pilate retraces the events that occurred before his very eyes on that fateful Friday: the Jews delivering Jesus to him, the account of the many miracles performed by the indicted man, the accusations, the sentence and crucifixion. Then, three days after, an unexpected resurrection («die tertio surrexit»), with the soldier on watch attesting that he had actually done so («nam et illum surrexisse testati sunt se vidisse»). He closes his letter by openly accusing the Jews:

«I have reported this lest anyone should lie about it and lest you should think that the lies of the Jews should be believed».

[In the original Latin text: «Haec ideo ingressi ne quis aliter mentiatur, et aestimes credendum mendaciis Iudaeorum»].

Fig. 69 - Witnesses to the Resurrection from the letter of Pilate to Emperor Claudius (manuscript Latin 1871, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 1)

Sure enough, this is not a letter that a prefect in charge for a Roman province might have ever written to the attention of his boss in Rome, full as it is of irrelevant information when read by a ruling Emperor, and manifestly concocted by an early-Christian hand so as to present itself as a proof of the Resurrection stated by an independent non-Christian witness, with the addition of clear anti-Jewish material.

But what is specifically of interest to us here is that, in this first available instance of a report, Pilate is not represented as a potential Christian yet.

However, the transformation of a heathen, Pontius Pilate, into an amazed witness to the Resurrection and eventually a convinced Christian is now underway.

Let's consider again the *Gospel of Nicodemus*, an apocryphal text which includes unrelated narratives traditionally labelled with the said inconsistent title: the first section, quite long, is known as *Gesta Pilati* or *Acta Pilati* (*Pilate's Deeds* or *Pilate's Report*), or even as *Gesta Salvatoris* (*The Deeds of the Saviour*): an apocryphal work whose origin is dated by scholars somewhere between the fourth and fifth century, with continual textual editing being performed throughout the subsequent centuries, owing to the great fortune experienced by the text across the Middle Ages, with hundreds and hundreds of surviving manuscripts written in various languages, including Greek, Latin, Aramaic, Armenian, Coptic, and others. In this article, we will display images taken from Codex 326 (1076), a most ancient manuscript dating back to the ninth century preserved at the Stiftsbibliothek of Einsiedeln Abbey, Switzerland.

Fig. 70 - The opening of the *Gesta Salvatoris* (or *Gesta Pilati*) from Codex 326 (1076) preserved at the Stiftsbibliothek of Einsiedeln Abbey, Switzerland (folium 11r)

In the *Gesta Pilati*, the positive tradition concerning the Roman prefect of Judaea develops even further, evolving into a representation of the Passion which is certainly more favourable to Pilate than that portrayed in the canonical Gospels. A Pilate who is remarkably near to a full conversion to the new Christian faith.

In this apocryphal writing, Pilate is amazed and moved at the sight of the stunning miracles that surrounds Jesus, to whom even the flags carried by the standard bearers at the prefect's palace bend as if they were honouring Him (folium 12r). Urged by the Jews, but finding no guilt in Jesus, he reacts angrily against them («Pilatus furore repletus», folium 13r). When they ask him to crucify Jesus, he openly replies «This is no fair request» («Non est bonum», folium 14r).

Fig. 71 - Pilatus opposing the requests by the Jews from the *Gesta Pilati* (Codex 326 (1076) preserved at the Stiftsbibliothek of Einsiedeln Abbey, Switzerland, folium 14r)

It is clear that, in the *Gesta Pilati*, the Roman governor does not want to condemn Him, so much so that he hopelessly appeals to the raging crowd: «[I see that] not all the people gathered here wants Him to die» («non omnis multitudo uult eum mori», folium 14r). But the chief priests and elders of the Jews have no intention to give up. And when Nicodemus the Pharisee speaks in favour of Jesus, the following interesting remarks are pronounced (folium 14v):

«The Jews told Nicodemus: 'You certainly have turned into one of His followers, considering that you so openly speak in his favour'. But Nicodemus replied: 'Perhaps you think that the governor, too, is now among His followers, owing to his words in Jesus' favour?'».

[In the original Latin text: «Dicunt iudaei nichodemo: tu discipulus eius factus es et verbum pro ipso facis. Dicit ad eos nichodemus: numquid et praeses discipulus eius factus est et verbum pro ipso facit?»].

The chasm between a prefect of Rome and a Christian believer is getting narrower and narrower: the *Gesta Pilati* clearly suggests that Pontius Pilate is more than a local administrators, as Jesus may have proceeded deeply in his heart. We are bordering Pilate's full conversion to Christianity.

Fig. 72 - Pontius Pilate suspected to be a Christian from the *Gesta Pilati* (Codex 326 (1076) preserved at the Stiftsbibliothek of Einsiedeln Abbey, Switzerland, folium 14v)

The accounts on Jesus's sanctity continue to flow in from the crowd. Pilate listens to several tales of miraculous deeds, he is fully convinced of his innocence, he utters harsh words against the pressing Jews. When at last Jesus dies on the Cross, and the sun disappears casting darkness over the whole land, the veil of the temple rent in twain from the top to the bottom, Pilate seems to fully believe, finally, in the holiness of the sentenced man (folium 16v):

«Pilate convened the Jews and said: 'Did you see what happened?' But they so replied to the governor: 'Just a solar eclipse as often happens'».

[In the original Latin text: «Convocans autem pilatus iudaeos dicit eis: vidistis quae facta sunt? responderunt praesidi: Eclipsis factum est solis secundum consuetudinem»].

Fig. 73 - Pilate beholds the miracles which followed Jesus' death from the *Gesta Pilati* (Codex 326 (1076) preserved at the Stiftsbibliothek of Einsiedeln Abbey, Switzerland, folium 16v)

Pontius Pilate is slowly walking his centuries-long road, gradually turning into an early, very early Christian.

There is a further hint to that ongoing conversion process in the *Anaphora Pilati* (*Pilate's Report*), a Greek text which allegedly contains, once more, the official report on the Passion written by Pontius Pilate and addressed to Emperor Tiberius in Rome. Of course, the *Anaphora* is nothing more than a traditional text which was put on parchment centuries after Pilate's death. Again, this text has no relation at all with a possible original written by Pilate himself in the first century; however the *Anaphora Pilati* offers another Christian-oriented interpretation of the content of the prefect's report, with a view to providing a convincing testimony to the Resurrection. Here is the Greek text as it appears in manuscript Grec 770 preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (folium 25r):

«To the most mightly, venerable, most divine, and most terrible, August Caesar, Pilate the governor of the East. I have, O most mighty, a narrative to give thee, on account of which I am seized with fear and trembling. For in the territory under my government, being one city named Jerusalem, the Jews delivered to me a man called Jesus...».

Fig. 74 - The initial invocation to Tiberius as contained in the *Anaphora Pilati* (manuscript Grec 770, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 25r)

After this grandiloquent opening, in a few pages Pilate recounts the events of that extraordinary Friday in Jerusalem. The Roman prefect voices all his amazement at the preternatural wonders which occurred after the death of Jesus:

«A great darkness took hold of all the world, because the sun was darkened, and the stars appeared but they did not shine; and the light of the moon appeared as blood [...] and there were great thunders [...] and amid the general terror dead men were seen that had risen from their graves [...] there was a loud voice from Heaven [...] men were seen who were great and tall in stature, clothed in garments of glory [...] they cried thus: Jesus was crucified and has come again to life [...] and many people of the Jews were swallowed up by the earth».

In the *Anaphora Pilati*, Pontius Pilate appears as an astonished witness to the Resurrection. And it is manifest that he is so shaken that he is not too far from crossing the threshold that leads from heathendom to the true faith (folium 27r):

«I was in great fear and trembling. I wrote all the things that I saw and happened. And I sent these things to thy Majesty, O Emperor [...] O Lord, I salute thee».

Fig. 75 - The final sentences of the *Anaphora Pilati* (manuscript Grec 770, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 27r)

With another apocryphal work, the *Paradosis Pilati* (*The hand-over of Pilate*), an ancient text written in Greek, whose dating is uncertain, we take a further step towards Pilate's consecration as a full Christian. The *Paradosis* is contained in the same manuscript Grec 770 which we already considered for the *Anaphora*, starting from folium 27v.

At the very moment of his harrowing death, which we will describe later in this series of articles, the former prefect of Judaea raises a desperate plea to the Heaven for him and his wife Procla:

«Pardon me, Lord, and your servant Procla, who stands with me in this hour of my death, whom you taught to prophesy that you must be benailed to the cross. [...] Pardon us and number us among your righteous ones».

Fig. 76 - The opening of the *Paradosis Pilati* (folium 27v) with the first sentence enlarged, and the final sentences (folium 29 r) with the words for 'Pilate's head' highlighted (manuscript Grec 770, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France)

And his prayer is answered, because an amazing miracle happens:

«Behold, when Pilate had finished his prayer, there sounded a voice from heaven, 'All generations and families of the Gentiles shall call you blessed, because in your governorship everything was fulfilled which the prophets foretold about me. And you yourself shall appear as my witness at my second coming».

Pilate as a righteous? Pilate as prophet? Pilate as a holy man? Doesn't it sound unbelievable, to our modern ears?

But the *Paradosis* goes even further: when Pilate is beheaded, «an angel of the Lord received his head». And brought it to Heaven.

Pontius Pilate as a saint. This is the astonishing conclusion of a mythical route that started at the moment of the Passion of Jesus Christ, in the first century, and ended today.

It did not end with the *Paradosis*. It ended its course right in our present days.

Because today Pontius Pilatus is, in actual reality, a saint. A recognised saint: St. Pilate. As we will see in the next article.

12. A governor and a saint

July, 2nd, save the date. In fact this is a very important day for Christians, as the Holy Roman Church celebrates many respectable saints, though totally undistinguished, like St. Processus and Martinianus, Virgin Saint Monegundes, St. Swithun and many other holy people listed in the *Martyrologium Romanum*.

However, on that very same day the ancient Ethiopian Orthodox Tewahedo Church, one of the largest Eastern Orthodox Churches and one of the most antique Christian confessions, keeps memory of a saint who is far more renowned.

It is St. Pontius Pilate.

In a contemporary edition of the *Ethiopian Synaxarion*, the Book of Saints of the Ethiopian Church, under the twenty-fifth day of the month of Säne (corresponding to our July, 2nd), we find in the listing the following holy man:

«On this day also died Pilate, the confessor. Salutation to Pilate who washed his hands of the Blood of Jesus Christ. [...] Glory be to God Who is glorified in His Saints. Amen».

Fig. 77 - Pontius Pilate celebrated as a saint in the *Synaxarium - The Book of the Saints of the Ethiopian Orthodox Tewahedo Church*, translated by the British philologist Ernest Alfred Wallis Budge in 1928 and reprinted by a contemporary Ethiopian church (pag. 593)

This sentence is drawn from sources that are far more ancient, which include manuscripts written in the Ethiopian language and dating to the sixteenth and eighteenth century, as reported by the great Italian scholar Ignazio Guidi in his work *Le Sinaxaire Éthiopien*, published in 1907 (in which the twenty-fifth day of the month of Säne is said to correspond to our June, 19th).

Fig. 78 - Pilate as a saint from Ignazio Guidi's *Le Sinaxaire Éthiopien* (*Patrologia Orientalis*, vol. 1, published in Paris in 1907, pag. 674-675)

Thus, a very ancient tradition, pertaining to the Eastern devotees, has been considering Pontius Pilatus as a saint. For centuries and centuries. And it is still considered so, as shown by the contemporary *Synaxarion*.

This odd, unexpected status - for the devotees of the Holy Roman Church - is the outcome of a long process, which began with the Gospels and proceeded through apocryphal texts such as the *Epistola Pilati*, the *Gesta Pilati*, the *Anaphora Pilati* and the *Paradosis Pilati*, supported in its course by early-Christian authors including Tertullianus, Eusebius of Caesarea, Paulus Orosius, Origen of Alexandria: all of them presenting Pilate as basically «innocent of the blood of this just person» (Matthew 27:24), that is of the blood of Jesus.

Because, according to this old tradition, Pontius Pilate, at the end of the story, began to believe in Jesus, after he had witnessed to the miracles that had taken place before and after His death. The prefect became a Christian, the governor turned into a prophet. The Roman ruler had glorified the mighty of God at last, and so he had become a saint.

All that started to happen since the very beginning of Christianity and despite the numerous existing literary statements concerning Pilate's

cowardness, ruthlessness, wickedness and basical mediocrity, as attested by the classical tradition (Philo of Alexandria, Flavius Josephus) and even the Gospels themselves.

For the blame for Jesus' death wasn't to be put on Pontius Pilate.

Instead, according to this ancient tradition, the true murderers of a God were the Jews: «see ye to it», as Pilate himself had told them (Matthew 27:24).

Why did the early-Christian community decide that this exorbitant guilt should lie entirely on the Jewish nation?

Even though it is outside the scope of the present paper to address the miserable history of Anti-Semitism, reasons appear to be manifold. Many scholars think that, in a very early phase of Christianity, wouldn't have been safe for the new religion to charge so great an accusation on a high-rank Roman citizen, a prominent official who was a direct report to the Emperor in Rome. Too powerful and dangerous was the Roman Empire to challenge it in such a straightforward way. On the other side, the Jews made up a feasible target, weak as they were in terms of both political and military strength. They also represented a competitor for the rising Christianity, an obstacle to the acquisition of new devotees in the very region where Jesus had lived and preached.

Anti-Semitism was just raising its awful head, and would ravage across the whole of Europe in the centuries and millennia to come. To further illustrate this gloomy context, we can also quote from another fourth-century theologian, St. Ephrem the Syrian, especially celebrated in the Eastern Orthodox Church, who was the author of many poetic hymns in Syriac who mentioned both Pilate and the Jews. In the hymn *On the Crucifixion* he wrote the following lines on Pilate as a righteous man:

«Thee also, O Title, that just man wrote - One of the Gentiles, on behalf of all the Gentiles - [...] Prophets for the Son from among the gentiles - [...] Prophecy cried out from among the Gentiles».

And in another hymn, *On Virginity*, he wrote that «[Pilate] who upon his tribunal washed his hands - [...] wast cleansed and purified - by [...] waters

of innocent dreams - The Nations shone fourth, purified and cleansed - but the [Jewish] Nation became black, defiled by that blood».

Fig. 79 - Pontius Pilate and the Jews as mentioned in fourth-century hymns by St. Ephrem the Syrian (from *Symbols of Church and Kingdom - A study in early Sirciac tradition* by Robert Murray, published in London in 2006, pag. 66)

Therefore, the whitewashing of the memory of Pontius Pilate fitted the objectives of a developing Christianity: Jesus Christ had been killed by the Jews, while the Roman prefect, as a result of a suitable cleanup, was turned into a righteous devotee and prophet. And the cleanup of his figure would have gone as far as full sanctity.

At least, in the eastern Christian tradition.

St. Pilate is worshipped by an Orthodox Church, the Ethiopian. Many of the apocryphal texts which introduce an almost Christian Pontius Pilate are written in Greek, and are intended for an eastern audience.

On the other side, the Holy Roman Church, in the western area of Europe, does not worship Pontius Pilate in the least. And it never did.

Because something very different has happened, across the centuries, in the western tradition. Pilate was not considered as a positive figure at all.

We will now start a brand new course spanning through the Middle Ages in Western Europe. A course of no sanctity and no holiness. A gloomy, sinister course.

And it is a course that will bring us, after many windings, up to the legends of the Lakes of Pilatus. In the very middle of the Italian Sibillini Mountain Range.

Fig. 80 - The Lakes of Pilate in the Sibillini Mountain Range, Italy

13. The fate of Pentheus

In our previous article, we described the journey across the centuries of an ancient tradition that portrays Pilatus, the prefect of Judaea who sentenced Jesus Christ to death, as a latent Christian, if not a full convert, and then a testimony to the Resurrection, a prophet and finally a saint.

This peculiar outcome, which can be traced across time up to present sanctity formally recognised by an eastern Orthodox church, can be faintly detected in western worship as well. However, in this case it is but a feeble remnant of the antique tradition we have already depicted.

Fig. 81 - Western Europe portrayed in a gorgeous miniature contained in a fifteenth-century edition of Ptolemy's *Cosmographia* published by Jacobus Angelus in Florence (manuscript Latin 4802, Bibliothèque Nationale de France. Département des Manuscrits, folium 74v)

In Western Europe, a similar hint to Pilate's innocence is found in the *Letter of Pilatus to Emperor Tiberius*, an apocryphal text written in Latin, possibly dating to as late as early Renaissance. It is reported by Barthélemy de Chasseneuz in his *Catalogus gloriae mundi, laudes, honores, excellentias* published in Lyon in 1546:

«I did not strive to the utmost of my power to prevent the loss and suffering of righteous blood, guiltless of every accusation. It was an injustice due to the malice of men».

[In the original Latin text: «pro viribus non restiterim, sanguinem iustum totius accusationis immunem, verum hominum malignitate inique»].

Fig. 82 - The letter of Pilatus to Emperor Tiberius as found in the *Catalogus gloriae mundi, laudes, honores, excellentias* by Barthélemy de Chasseneuz, published in Lyon in 1546 (Quarta Pars, pag. 90)

Another example can be retrieved in a text we already mentioned earlier in this series of articles: St. Jerome's *Commentary on Matthew* edited by Erasmus of Rotterdam and published in 1537, a work that contains the following interpolation by Erasmus:

«Pilate gave multiple opportunities for freeing the Savior: first by offering a thief for a just man; then by adding: "What then shall I do about Jesus who is called Christ? [...] what evil has he done?" In saying this, Pilate absolved Jesus. [...] Thus, in the washing of his hands, the works of the Gentiles are cleansed, and in some manner he estranges us from the impiety of the Jews».

[In the original Latin text: «Multas liberandi salvatoris Pilatus occasiones dedit. Primum latrone iusto conferens. Deinde inferens: Quid igitur faciam de Iesu qui dicitur Christus [...] Quid eum mali fecit. Hoc dicendo Pilatus absolvit Iesum. [...] Ut in lavacro manuum eius, gentilium opera purgarentur, et ab impietate Iudaeorum»].

However, the listed examples have more to do with a widespread racist sentiment held within the Christian community than the absolution of Pontius Pilate's guilts.

In Western Europe, Pilate has never become a saint.

Since early Christianity, the Church of Rome had to deal with the opinion expressed by a pagan enemy of old, the Greek philosopher Celsus. As early as the second-century, he attacked the new expanding religion with his treatise *On The True Doctrine*, in which, according to the extant excerpts that can be retrieved in Origen's response *Against Celsum* (Book II, Chapter 34), he highlighted Pontius Pilate's manifest culpability in the case Jesus had truly been a divine being, which he definitely did not believe:

«The person [Pilate] that condemned Him didn't endure any punishment, comparable to that of Pentheus, who was deprived of his senses and torn to pieces».

Fig. 83 - The sentence on Pilate and Pentheus taken from Origen of Alexandria's *Kata Kelsou* (manuscript Grec 616, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 76v, with the Greek words for 'Pentheus, deprived of his senses and torn to pieces' highlighted)

So, since the very beginning of the whole story, it was a pagan author who hit the nail of the head: if Jesus Christ had really been the Son of a God, Pontius Pilate's guilt would simply be immense, the same guilt which lay with Pentheus, the King of Thebes who opposed Dionysus and pushed

himself as far as to imprison a deity, according to the tale told by Euripides in his tragic play *The Bacchae*.

He was slain and dismembered by the members of his own family.

Why hadn't Pontius Pilate undergone the same ghastly, harrowing doom?

Despite his feeble attempts at setting Jesus free, his subsequent alleged conversion, his putting the blame on Jews, his prospective sanctity, and his unnatural placement within an Orthodox calendar of saints, the Roman prefect of Judaea would not escape his own predestined fate.

Fig. 84 - Pontius Pilate and the burden of guilt

His destiny was already written. And we will see, as the centuries rolled along, that his doom was inevitable. It was just a matter of time.

14. The hands of the Fiend

Despite an early-Christian tendency to consider Pontius Pilate as a prospective convert to the new religion, with a view to putting the blame of

Jesus' death on the Jews, there was someone who was working to meet a different target.

The reputation of the Christians had to be spoiled. And Pilate could help achieving this task.

At the beginning of the fourth century, forged versions of the reports written by Pilate to Tiberius on the Passion began to circulate. And the forgery was intended for the widest distribution amid the people:

«The measures and the decrees of the cities against us, and copies of the imperial edicts appended to these, were engraved and erected on brazen tablets, a course never before adopted against us anywhere. The children also in the schools had the names of Jesus and Pilate, and the acts forged in derision, in their mouths the whole day. [...] Having therefore forged certain Acts of Pilate, respecting our Saviour, full of every kind of blasphemy against Christ, these, with the consent of the Emperor, they sent through the whole of the empire subject to him, commanding at the same time by ordinances in every place and city, and the adjacent districts, that they should be openly posted to the view of all persons, and that the schoolmasters should give them to their scholars to study and commit to memory, instead of their customary lessons».

Fig. 85 - The passages on Pontius Pilate's forged acts taken from Book IX of Eusebius of Caesarea's *Historia Ecclesiae* (from a manuscript Latin translation published in Utrecht in 1474, folia 162v and 161r)

The listed events are reported by Eusebius of Caesarea (*Historia Ecclesiae*, Book IX), who stresses the point that someone had fabricated a fake version of Pontius Pilate's reports, in an attempt to ridicule the new Christian faith and devotees. The forgery was badly concocted, as the same Eusebius notes (Book 1):

«From all this we can manifestly see the mischievous forgery of the reports [allegedly written by Pontius Pilate], that have been recently fabricated against our Lord Jesus Christ, and in which the very same information concerning the dates shows the falsehood thereof. For such reports falsely affirm that the passion of the Saviour happened during the fourth consulship of Tiberius, which occurred during the seventh year of his rule. This is a patent fake, because at that time Pilatus had not been sent to Judaea as a prefect yet».

Fig. 86 - Another passage on the forged acts of Pilate as taken from Book I of Eusebius of Caesarea's *Historia Ecclesiae* (from a manuscripted Latin translation published in Utrecht in 1474, folium 23v)

According to Eusebius, the forgery had been commissioned by the highest political levels in Rome: the fake version of the 'Acta Pilati' were part of an anti-Christian policy pursued by Emperor Maximinus II, who ruled at the beginning of the fourth century.

In this ever-changing political framework, it is no surprise that the figure of Pilate, blurred and subject to conflicting thrusts which portrayed him as a near-Christian and an anti-Christian at the same time, was slowly moving towards a much less favourable representation.

Even though fourth-century bishop Eusebius of Caesarea, in his *Historia Ecclesiae* had depicted an amazed, bewildered Pontius Pilate reporting to his Emperor about the final hours in the life of Jesus, as if he were on the verge of a possible conversion to the new faith, that same Eusebius was the first to start raising doubts on a pacific ending of Pilate's unholy life (Book II, Chapter VII). We read his words from eleventh-century manuscript Grec 1431 preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (folia 33r and 33v), in which we highlighted the Greek words for 'Pilate' and 'with his own hand':

«Pilate himself, who was an unjust judge to the Saviour, is reported to have fallen into such misfortunes under Caius [Caligula] that he stabbed himself with his own hand, leaving his wicked life. Certainly he couldn't have escaped the divine vengeance».

For the first time, even for Christians Pilate is no prospective convert anymore. He begins to be considered as a wicked official, who is held responsible for what had happened to Jesus Christ, the Son of God. And divine punishment starts reaching him, in the most typical form of self-destruction, namely suicide.

Fig. 87 - The excerpt on Pilate's suicide as it appears in Eusebius of Caesarea's *Historia Ecclesiae* (manuscript Grec 1431, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, folia 33r and 33v with Greek words for 'Pilate' and 'with his own hand' highlighted)

It is at the end of the fourth century, with the Niceno-Constantinopolitan Creed, adopted at the First Council of Constantinople in the year 381, that the early-Christian Church starts mentioning the name of Pontius Pilate in an official statement of belief. And certainly the mention does not appear to be as a fully positive quote, even though it does not put any manifest blame on the Roman prefect:

«[...] He [Jesus] was crucified for us under Pontius Pilate, and suffered, and was buried, and the third day he rose again [...]».

Nonetheless, the way is now paved for a new, darker representation of Pilate's controversial shadow.

In that same period, in Milan, Italy, an illustrious bishop, Aurelius Ambrosius, known today as St. Ambrose, wrote stern, disapproving words on Pilate in his *Expositio evangelii secundum Lucam* (*Commentary on the Gospel according to Luke*, Book X):

Fig. 88 - Pontius Pilate as a wicked judge in Aurelius Ambrosius's *Expositio evangelii secundum Lucam* (from *Sancti Ambrosii Mediolanensis Episcopi Opera*, Volume III, 1661, pag. 219)

«Sure Pilate washed his hands, but this did not diluted the facts; a judge must never give in to malevolence or fear, lest he barter innocent blood [...] He did not restrain from uttering an unholy sentence. So I reckon we find in him the type of all judges who condemn those whom they consider not guilty».

[In the original Latin text: «Lavit quidem manus Pilatus, sed facta non diluit; iudex enim nec invidiae cedere debuit nec timori, ut sanguinem innocentem addiceret. [...] nec sic a sacrilega sententia temperavit. Similiter in hoc typum omnium iudicum arbitror esse praemissum, qui damnaturi essent eos quos innoxios aestimarent»].

And even harsher words Ambrosius put down against Pilate in his *Enarrationes in XII Psalmos Davidicos* (*Explanations on twelve David's Psalms*, Psalm CXVIII, Sermo XX, 38):

Fig. 89 - Pilate and the power of darkness in Aurelius Ambrosius's *Enarrationes in XII Psalmos Davidicos* (from *Sancti Ambrosii Mediolanensis Episcopi Opera*, Volume II, printed in Venice in 1748, pag. 680-681)

«And Pilate said to Lord Jesus: 'I have power to crucify thee, and have power to release thee'. O man, you arrogate to yourself something you do not own. [...] Listen to what justice says: 'I shall not do nothing by myself'. [...] By your own voice, Pilate, you chain yourself, by your own sentence you condemn yourself. [...] Evil power is one which makes lawful what lawful is not. This is the power of darkness, a power that doesn't see the truth, and holds it in contempt».

[In the original Latin text: «Et Pilatus dicebat ad dominum Jesum: 'Potestatem habeo dimittendi te, et potestatem habeo crucifigendi te'. Usurpas, o homo, potestatem quam non habet. [...] Audi quid justitia dicat: 'Non possum a me facere quidquam'. [...] Tua, Pilate, voce constringeris, tua damnatis sententia. [...] Mala potestas licere quod non liceat. Potestas ista tenebrarum est, verum non videre, sed spernere»].

We are getting nearer and nearer to a fiendish representation of the fifth prefect of Roman-occupied Judaea: a wicked judge, whose hands are dripping with the blood of the Son of God, despite the ineffective washing he had publicly staged in an effort to shun his own responsibility and guilt.

A man of darkness. A man of evil. A man who just condemned himself. Out of his same sentence, out of his own nasty, ungodly behaviour.

But the final, decisive blow against Pontius Pilate will be struck by another prominent member of the Western Church, a Pope and a saint: Gregory I the Great.

In his *Quadragesima homiliarum de diversis lectionibus evangelii* (*Forty sermons on various passages from the Gospels*), dating to the final decade of the sixth century, St. Gregory delivers a sermon (XVI) on a passage taken from the Gospel of Matthew, in which Jesus is tempted by the devil. And this is the very point where he treads the ultimate barrier which separates Pilate from his final destination and doom.

For the first time ever, St. Gregory openly states the fiendish nature of Pontius Pilate:

«Certainly the Fiend is the very head of all evil men: and all evil men are the limbs to this head. And wasn't Pilate a limb of the Devil?».

[In the original Latin text: «Certe iniquorum omnium caput diabolus est: et huius capitis membra sunt omnes iniqui. An non diaboli membrum fuit Pilatus?»].

Fig. 90 - Pilate as a limb of the Fiend in St. Gregory's *Quadragesima homiliarum de diversis lectionibus evangelii*, from a book containing works by the Pope published in Paris in 1523 (folium CCCVIII)

And this ghastly correspondence is further stated in another work by Gregory the Great. In Book III, Cap. XII of the *Expositio moralis in beatum Job*, a commentary on the Book of Job, he writes the following sentence:

Fig. 91 - Pilate as a limb of the Fiend in St. Gregory's *Expositio moralis in beatum Job*, from a book containing works by the Pope published in Paris in 1523 (folium XIII)

«Limbs of the Fiend are those, which are joined to him in perverse life. No doubt Pilate is manifestly a limb of the Fiend: Pilate, who did not recognize the Lord who was offering himself for our salvation to the utmost sacrifice of death».

[In the original Latin text: «Sathanae membra sunt omnes, qui ei perverse vivendo iunguntur. Membrum quippe eius Pilatus extitit, qui usque ad mortis extrema venientem in redemptionem nostram dominum non cognovit»].

These are the words that will mark the Roman prefect for the centuries to come: Pontius Pilate, a limb of the unholy, loathsome body of Satan.

And this idea will play a fundamental part in our legends, known throughout the Middle Ages, concerning the many resting places of Pilate. Resting places which include the Sibillini Mountain Range, in Italy.

15. Recalled and punished

In this series of articles, we are exploring the figure and myth of Pontius Pilate, the Roman prefect who was ruling Judaea when Jesus Christ underwent his harrowing Passion.

Fig. 92 - Pontius Pilate recalled to Rome

As per our previous descriptions of the literary tradition concerning Pilate, we saw that a peculiar line can be retrieved across the centuries which depicts Pontius Pilate as a man who was struck and amazed at the vision of the miracles which occurred during and after the Passion, so much so that

he began to be considered as a sort of prospective Christian or even as a full convert to the new rising religion; this tradition evolved, especially in the Eastern churches, up to unexpected results, including celebration as a saint by the Ethiopian Orthodox Church.

In the Western tradition, the course of Pilate's travel through literary history has proved to be quite different, with a different outcome altogether.

We started from the bishop of Milan, St. Ambrose, who in the fourth century highlighted the unholy behaviour of Pontius Pilate, an unrighteous judge acting in darkness. And then we saw the blood-curdling words written by Pope Gregory I the Great in the sixth century, who portrayed Pilate as a veritable limb of Satan, fully controlled by the evil will of the Fiend.

This is the visible result of a process that was already on its way during the preceding centuries, marked by a number of literary witnesses which present Pilate as being recalled to Rome by his Emperor to suffer punishment, out of his wicked management of Jesus Christ's Passion and death.

And this is no matter of addressing a mere report to Tiberius, as mentioned by Tertullianus, Eusebius of Caesarea and Paulus Orosius: we now see Pontius Pilate summoned before the imperial ruler, and condemned for having handed over Jesus, the Son of God, to the Jews, after having carelessly washed his hands before the mob.

We already saw the *Paradosis Pilati* (*The hand-over of Pilate*), an ancient apocryphal text written in Greek, in which Pilate is recalled to Rome in chains:

«When the report arrived in Rome and was read to Caesar, with many people listening to it too, all stood in amazement at the news of the darkness and the earthquake that had come upon the world because of the lawlessness of Pilate. Caesar, in rage, ordered his soldiers to bring Pilate to him as a prisoner».

In the *Paradosis*, the Roman prefect is held guilty of his rash, coward handling of such a crucial matter as the trial of the Son of God:

«When Pilate was brought to Rome [... the Emperor] ordered Pilate to stand forward and said to him: 'How could you dare to act as you did, you most impious man, if you had the chance to see the great signs concerning that man? With your wicked behaviour, you have destroyed the whole world. [...] You should have guarded him [Jesus] from the Jews [...] for it is clear from the those signs that Jesus was the Christ, the king of the Jews».

The Emperor utters many other enraged words against his former prefect, and finally he sentences him to death:

«As this man [Pilate] raised his hand against the righteous man called Christ, so shall he fall in the same way and find no salvation».

Fig. 93 - The sentence pronounced by the Emperor upon Pontius Pilate from the *Paradosis Pilati* (manuscript Grec 770, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 28b)

Despite the accusations, in the above narration the tradition which depicts Pilate as a Christian convert is fully present («I myself was convinced by

his deeds that he is greater than all the gods whom we worship», he tells the Emperor) and in the very moment of his beheading an angel takes his falling head and takes it to heaven, as we already described in a previous article.

The more we venture ourselves into the Middle Ages, the more the legend of a Pontius Pilate recalled in Rome and punished for his role in the Passion expands and gets stronger.

And, at the same time, we get closer and closer to the account made by Antoine de la Sale, centuries later, on the Lakes of Pilatus and the Sibillini Mountain Range.

What are we referring to? Let's go and see it.

Fig. 94 - The opening page and the sentence on the revenge on the enemies of Jesus Christ from the *Vindicta Salvatoris* (manuscript Latin 5327, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folia 55r and 56v)

We are now going to consider the *Vindicta Salvatoris* (*The vengeance of the Saviour*), a medieval text dating to the High Middle Ages and presenting various textual versions, which we read from a very ancient manuscript: Latin 5327 preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France, which comes to us from the tenth century.

The *Vindicta* describes, with the introduction of conspicuous confusion among unrelated historical events and rulers, a campaign against the town of Jerusalem carried out jointly by Vespasian and Titus, the latter being not the well-known Emperor's son but instead the ruler of «Burdigala», today's Bordeaux in Aquitaine, France, a town subject to Emperor Tiberius. The war is waged to avenge the murder of Jesus Christ, so that «they know that no other Lord is equal to Him on the whole world» («ut cognoscant quia non est similis eius dominus super faciem terrae», in the original Latin text, folium 56v).

Jerusalem is taken after a siege which lasts seven years. The town's inhabitants are slaughtered by the Romans. Then, we find again our poor prefect, who seems to be still alive and kicking under the reign of Vespasian (folium 57v):

Fig. 95 - The excerpt on Pilate seized and imprisoned from the *Vindicta Salvatoris* (manuscript Latin 5327, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 57v)

«Pilate was seized and [...] put in a prison in Damascus under the custody of four squads made up by four soldiers each, who were standing before the prison's door».

[In the original Latin text: «Et adprehenderunt Pilatum [...] et miserunt eum in Damasco in carcere et miserunt ei custodes quattuor quaternionum ante portam carceris»].

Following the listed events, Tiberius sends his envoy Velosianus from Rome to Judaea to carry out an enquiry into the death of Jesus. And, when he questions Pilate, he addresses him with the following words (folium 58v): «'Why did you murder the Son of God?' Pilate replied: 'His fellow-countrymen delivered Him to me'. So Velosianus said: 'For sure you will die for this'» (in the original Latin text: «'Quare interfecisti filium dei?' Pilatus autem dixit: 'Gens sua tradiderunt illum'. Velosianus autem dixit: 'Manifeste moriturus eris'»).

Fig. 96 - Pilate doomed to death in an excerpt taken from the *Vindicta Salvatoris* (manuscript Latin 5327, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 58v)

Then we find a reference to the fate of Pontius Pilate, as it will appear more clearly in later texts: by the order of Tiberius, Pilatus, that cursed man («hunc hominem maledictum»), is thrown into a prison called 'Gehenna' («in Gehenne carcere»), amid the most harrowing torments, locked and sealed there so that the earth shall not see him never again («in tormentorum et sub claude eum sub sigillo annulum et amplius non aperiat super terram») (folium 61r). We will later see that 'Gehenna' is not the place mentioned in the Old Testament and Gospels as the destination for evil people and sinners, but rather a corrupted reference to the ancient town of Vienne, in Gaul (France), which plays a major role in the legend of Pontius Pilate.

So, this narration does not provide a full account of Pilate's execution; yet, once again, in the Western medieval tradition Pontius Pilate is fully held guilty of the killing of Jesus Christ, with no space for sanctity or prospect Christianity.

Fig. 97 - Pilate sentenced as described in the *Vindicta Salvatoris* (manuscript Latin 5327, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 61r)

In addition to that, it is important to stress the fact that here we stumble into something we already know. We find Pilate and Vespasian together, actually an account that is similar to the one reported by Antoine de la Sale in his fifteenth-century *The paradise of Queen Sibyl*:

Fig. 98 - Pilate and the vengeance of Jesus' death from Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 2v)

«Tales are told that when Titus son of Vespasian, the Emperor of Rome, had crushed down the town of Jerusalem, which some say that it was made to avenge the death of Our Lord Jesus Christ [...] when he came back to

Rome he brought with him Pilate who at that time was an officier at the said town of Jerusalem».

[In the original French text: «se compte que quant titus de vespasien empereur de romme eut destruite la cite de Jherusalem la quelle aucuns disent que ce fut pour la vengeance de la mort Nostre Sieu Jhesuscrist [...] au retour que fist a romme, mena avecques soy pillate qui pour ce temps estoit officier en la ditte cite de Jherusalem»].

Clues begin to fit in, elements start joining each other. Antoine de la Sale, with his accompanying peasants, is just reporting an older tale, an instance of whom is the *Vindicta Salvatoris*, in which Pontius Pilate lives side by side with Vespasian and Titus, who are looking for revenge for Jesus' death.

Is this the only clue that leads us towards the Sibillini Mountain Range, Antoine de la Sale and the legendary tale on Pilate and his lake?

Not at all. Because something very remarkable also happens in a different text which describes the death of Pilatus.

It is the *Rescriptum Tiberii*, also known as the *Epistola Tiberii ad Pilatum*, a Greek text which scholars date to the eleventh century on the basis of linguistic considerations (we take a version of it from folia 282v and 283r of manuscript Grec 1771 preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France). A transcript from Greek is found in M. R. James' *Apocrypha Anecdota* (Part II, pag. 78) and a translation into English is provided by Roger Pearse.

In this letter, allegedly addressed to Pilate by Tiberius, after the customary accusations uttered by the Emperor against his prefect, he informs the governor that «just as you condemned this one unjustly and delivered him to death, I in turn will deliver you to death justly». Then, Pilate and all the leaders of the Jews, including Archelaus, brother to Herod Antipas, and the chief priests Caiaphas and Annas, are seized and taken to Rome. Pilate is «bricked up in a certain cave, and abandoned there».

So Pontius Pilate ends up his life buried in an underground place (oddly enough, in this narrative he will be killed by a stray arrow which penetrates into the cave through a hole after having been shot by the same Tiberius

during a deer hunt). This is a prefiguration of the lakes and pits that will conceal his body on several mountains in France, Switzerland and Italy.

Fig. 99 - The *Epistola Tiberii ad Pilatum* (manuscript Grec 1771, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folia 282v and 283r)

However, what we find here is even more interesting. Because, according to the *Rescriptum Tiberii*, while Archelaus is impaled and Annas is sealed into the skin of an ox subsequently exposed to the scorching sun, it is Caiaphas who foretells the peculiar doom that Pontius Pilate will meet in later tales: during his journey towards Rome, the chief priest dies suddenly when in the island of Crete; and when they try to bury his corpse, the ground refuses to receive it, and casts him out.

This is no less than a first instance of that remarkable feature which will always mark Pilate's resting places: storms, as described by Antoine de la Sale in his *The paradise of Queen Sibyl*, and hail and vapours, and a

general commotion of the earth that seems to erupt with violence from the very ground.

Fig. 100 - The Greek words for 'Pilate' as they appear in the *Epistola Tiberii ad Pilatum* (manuscript Grec 1771, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folia 282v and 283r)

A ground which does not seem to be happy at all to harbour the dead body of Pilate. One of the limbs of Satan.

16. An excruciating death

As our investigation proceeds further into the centuries of the Middle Ages, the figure of Pontius Pilate increasingly darkens, in a vortex of different Emperors, punishments and final dooms for the prefect who presided over the trial and death of Jesus Christ.

In the seventh century, a Greek chronicler, John of Antioch, wrote a history of the world called *Historia chronike*, of which only fragmentary excerpts have reached our present times. Specific passages are found in a collection of Greek texts compiled by Bizantyne Emperor Constantine VII Porphyrogenitus, whose title is *On virtues and vices* and which is present in a single manuscript only (Codex Turonensis 980 preserved at the Municipal Library of Tours, France - Fig. 1).

Fig. 101 - The opening of *De virtutibus et vitiis*, which contains excerpts from John of Antioch's *Historia chronike* as present in the Codex Turonensis 980 (folium 151r) preserved at the Municipal Library of Tours

In a passage concerning Emperor Nero, we find the following words that reports about the punishment of Pilate:

«Nero dedicated himself to the study of philosophy, and he was eager to know about the Christ, who he thought was still alive. But when he happened to know that the Jews had crucified him, he was so irritated that he commanded that Annas and Caiaphas and Pilate be brought in chains before him. [...] Nero had Pilate imprisoned [...] and soon afterwards he had his head cut off, because Pilate had been so bold as to sentence to death so grand a man without any permission by his king».

ΝΕΡΩΝ.

Exc. De virt. p. 809 : Ὅτι βασιλεύοντος νέου τοῦ Νέρωνος Βούρρος καὶ Σενέκας διώκουν τὰ πράγματα. Ὁ δὲ λόγοις ἐσχόλαζε φιλοσόφους, καὶ τὰ περὶ τοῦ Χριστοῦ κατεμάθανεν. Ἐτι γὰρ ἐνόμιζεν αὐτὸν τοῖς ἀνθρώποις συναναστρέφεται. Καὶ μαθὼν ὅτι ὑπὸ τῶν Ἰουδαίων ἐσταυρώθη, ἠγανάκτησε. Καὶ προσέταξεν ἔλθειν τοὺς ἱερεῖς Ἄνναν καὶ Καϊάφραν καὶ αὐτὸν Πιλάτον, τὸν ἄρχοντα τότε γενόμενον, σιδηροδεσμίους. Καὶ [καθίσας ἐπὶ τῆς συγκλήτου] τὰ περὶ αὐτοῦ πεπραγμένα κατεμάθανεν. Οἱ οὖν περὶ τὸν Ἄνναν καὶ Καϊάφραν ἔλεγον, ὅτι « Ἡμεῖς τοῖς νόμοις αὐτὸν παρεδούκαμεν, καὶ εἰς καθοσίωσιν οὐχ ἠμάρτομεν. Ὁ γὰρ Πιλάτος ὢν ἄρχων ὅσα ἠβουλήθη ἐπραξε. » Καὶ τοῦτον ἐν τῷ δεσμωτηρίῳ κατέκλεισε, τοὺς δὲ περὶ τὸν Ἄνναν καὶ Καϊάφραν ἀπέλυσε. [Ἦμαρ δὲ τότε καὶ Σίμων ὁ Μάγος. Καὶ διαλεγόμενον Πέτρου καὶ Σίμωνος παρουσίᾳ Νέρωνος, ἤχθη Πιλάτος ἀπὸ τοῦ δεσμωτηρίου· καὶ παρισταμένων τῶν τριῶν τῷ Νέρωνι, ἔρωτᾷ τὸν Σίμονα· « Σὺ εἶ ὁ Χριστός; » Ὁ δὲ λέγει· « Ναί. » Εἶτα ἔρωτᾷ τὸν Πέτρον· « Σὺ εἶ ὁ Χριστός; »

Ὁ δὲ λέγει· « Οὐ· ἐμοῦ γὰρ παρισταμένου εἰς τὸν οὐρανὸν ἀνελήφθη. » Ἠρώτησε δὲ καὶ τὸν Πιλάτον, ποῖός ἐστιν ἐκ τούτων ὁ λεγόμενος Χριστός. Καὶ εἶπεν· « Οὐδὲ εἰς· ὁ μὲν γὰρ Πέτρος μαθητὴς αὐτοῦ γέγονε, καὶ εἰσηγήθη παρ' ἐμοῦ ὡς μαθητὴς αὐτοῦ, καὶ ἠρνήσατο αὐτὸν λέγων· « Οὐκ οἶδα τὸν ἄνθρωπον. » καὶ ἀπέλυσε αὐτόν. Οὗτος δὲ ὁ Σίμων οὐδαμῶς ἐγνωσταί μοι, οὐδεμίαν δὲ ἔχει ὁμοιότητα πρὸς ἐκείνον· ἔστι γὰρ οὗτος καὶ Αἰγύπτιος καὶ ἐμπληθὴς καὶ κατάκομος καὶ μέλας, παντελῶς τῆς ἐκείνου μορφῆς ἀλλότριος. » Ἀγανακτήσας οὖν ὁ βασιλεὺς κατὰ μὲν τοῦ Σίμωνος, ὡς ψευσαμένου καὶ εἰπόντος ἑαυτὸν Χριστόν· κατὰ δὲ τοῦ Πέτρου, ὡς ἀρνησαμένου τὸν διδάσκαλον, ἐξέβαλεν αὐτοὺς ἐκ τοῦ συνεδρίου· τὸν δὲ Πιλάτον τῆς κεφαλῆς ἀπέτεμε, ὡς τηλικούτου ἀνθρώπου ἀνελεῖν τολμήσαντα δίχα βασιλικῆς καλεύσεως. Καὶ μετὰ ταῦτα Πέτρον μὲν ἐσταύρωσε, Παῦλον δὲ τῆς κεφαλῆς ἀπέτεμε.

Fig. 102 - The excerpt on Nero and Pontius Pilate from John of Antioch's *Historia chronike* as reported in the Codex Turonensis 980 (transcribed by Carl Müller in *Fragmenta Historicum Graecorum*, Vol. IV, published in 1851 in Paris, pag. 574)

A similar narration is found in a wondrous Byzantine work called *Suda* or *Soudas*, the amazing encyclopedic collection of some 30,000 entries written around the tenth century and including a bounty of valuable information on the ancient world and many quotes from classical authors that otherwise would have gone lost. Under the entry 'Nero', which we read from a 1581 edition in Latin, we retrieve the same tale we already found in John of Antioch, with the following unexpected variations:

«Nero, irritated, threw Pilate into prison [...]. Simon the Magus was then at his prime. And when Peter and Simon were arguing in the presence of Nero, Pilate was brought from the prison. And when the three were standing beside Nero, he asked Simon, 'Are you the Christ?' and he said, 'Yes I am'. Next he asked Peter, 'Or, are you the Christ instead?' and Peter said, 'No; I was standing beside him when he was taken up into heaven'. And [Nero] asked Pilate, 'Which out of these men is the one called Christ?'. And he said, 'Neither one; for on the one hand, Peter was one of his disciples and [...] he denied him, saying, 'I do not know the man'. [...] On the other hand, this Simon was in no way known to me, and he has nothing in resemblance to that one, this Simon seems to me of Egyptian origin

instead [...]'. Therefore, the Emperor, in rage, on the one hand against Simon, having cheated by lies and having said himself [to be] Christ, on the other hand against Peter, having denied his teacher, threw them out from the council. He cut off Pilate's head, as one daring to kill such an illustrious man without the Emperor's command».

Fig. 103 - The entry on 'Nero' as found in a Latin translation of *Suidas*, published in Basel in 1581 (pag. 618)

Pilatus, Tiberius, Vespasian, Nero, St. Peter and Simon the Magus, the self-styled wizard described in the Acts of the Apostles, who, according to an apocryhal tradition, resided in Rome and performed miracles like Jesus. The more we advance into the Middle Ages, the more the tales about the now legendary figure of Pilate pile up one after the other, with frequent variations as each account incorporates fragments of previous versions and adds further fanciful details to the whole story. Clearly enough, multiple flows of oral narratives are undergoing different transformations and combinations, as the centuries roll by and Pilate continues to arouse the interest of fascinated audiences across Europe, both in the East and in the West.

In the year 1050, a Byzantine historian, George Kedrenos, also known as Cedrenus, reached unprecedented levels of cruelty when describing the excruciating death which had been experienced by Pontius Pilate. Here is what he writes in his *Synopsis historion*, as taken from a Latin edition published in 1566:

«According to some sources, under the rule of Gaius Caesar, Pontius Pilate was subject to several misfortunes, so much so that he committed suicide; others say that, after having being accused before Caesar on his deeds with Jesus by Mary Magdalene, he was sealed within a skin of an ox together with a rooster, a viper and a monkey, the way Romans used to do, and then exposed to the scorching sun; finally, there are many who assert he died after having been flayed alive as a goatskin».

Fig. 104 - Pontius Pilate undergoing the 'poena cullei' as reported by Cedrenus in his *Synopsis historion* (from a Latin edition published in Basel in 1566)

This crude description is not also reminiscent of the deadly punishment suffered by the Jewish high priest Annas in the *Rescriptum Tiberii*, but also of the most famous 'poena cullei' ('punishment in a leather sack'), in use for centuries across the Roman Empire for parricides, and widely documented

in several classical sources, in some cases with the addition of a fourth animal, a dog.

This tale shows that Pilate has been considered, in some traditions, as a most wicked criminal, deserving the atrocious sanction devised for those who kill their own father.

What is going on with Pontius Pilate, in such early centuries of the Middle Ages?

The remarkable fact is that a narrative framework is slowly emerging from the many tales, both literary and oral, which circulated in Europe as to the Roman prefect who did not protect Jesus Christ from his excruciating Passion.

The emerging tale was that Pilate had actually received the reward he had deserved, in the form of a brutal, merciless death, or even as a desperate suicide.

This meant that his corpse had to be disposed of.

Some burial place was now needed, so that the tales could be fitted with a suitable conclusion.

Fig. 105 - A burial place for Pontius Pilate

And a burial place actually pops up. One we already know.

However, this is not a lake in the Italian Sibillini Mountain Range. This is Vienne, France.

Michele Sanvico

END OF PART 2

**Please refer to Part 1 and Part 3
for the continuation of this research paper**